

EDUCATION OF A PERFECT GENERATION AS THE BASIC PRINCIPLE OF PRE-SCHOOL PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCE

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Abstract: the article highlights the fact that the education of the mature generation is the highest gift of human experience, the role and significance of preschool pedagogy from the point of view of providing services and training specialists in this direction.

Keywords: education, ideal generation, preschool pedagogy, perfect person.

As noted by enlightener Abdulla Awlani, "Education is a matter of either life or death for us: either salvation or destruction: either happiness or disaster." If we look at the history of mankind, there has been pedagogic activity in all periods. The birth of a person is not only a natural-biological event consisting of birth, but after birth, rising to the level of development of one's time, acquiring the existing socio-historical experience, determining one's place in society, being an active participant in the historical process. must become a participant, that is, receive education. In this process, the older generation begins to give its experience of life, struggle and work, knowledge and skills to the younger generations, that is, the process of development, formation and maturation of a newborn human child is guided and managed. This was done through a social phenomenon called education. As the society developed, the need to produce mature, well-rounded individuals grew and changed, renewed, and served the society.

The science of pedagogy began to appear in the process of theoretical

understanding, generalization and application of experiences in the field of education and upbringing of young generations at various stages of society. The science of modern preschool pedagogy has become a science that provides knowledge and information about the goals and tasks of education, state education standards, methods of education and training, forms of organization, and its laws in general.

As soon as a person is created and appears, he realizes that knowledge and educational qualities are the most necessary conditions and means for him to live. Because education is aimed at each person. After all, the material-spiritual structure of the world, its construction, its development, the material-spiritual living conditions and opportunities of a person are inextricably linked with his mental, moral, and physical condition.

That is why nature's ability to ensure human existence, existence, and happiness is directly related to its mental, moral, and physical development and growth. The problems in nature and society direct humanity to its spiritual and mental development and reveal new treasures to it. The two qualities listed above form the basis of the quality of a perfect human being. If the qualities of a perfect person are summed up and embodied in the sciences in the field of education, they are mainly three:

1. Good intention, thought;
2. Kind words, politeness;
3. Good work consists of good activity.

These three qualities are the main goal of education. This main goal is to improve the qualities of perfection in people, young people, professionals, to equip young people with modern, moral-practical education, qualifications, and skills, and to create science, knowledge, and skills suitable for each field in professionals. shows that pedagogy has expanded the foundations of modern science.

Since the subject of modern preschool pedagogy is a science that prepares specialists who arm children with comprehensive knowledge of modern laws,

content, methods, and means of education, its methodological foundations are the goals and tasks of the individual in the material and spiritual development of the world. Its perfection comes from the laws of harmony and the state's modern policy. Preschool pedagogy is a network pedagogy aimed at preschoolers in the subject system. This network studies the laws of the educational process carried out in preschool educational institutions.

All the unique ways of teaching preschool pedagogy serve to raise a mature generation. In this regard, general psychology is inextricably linked with the sciences of youth psychology. After all, the science of psychology explains the laws of mental development of a person at different ages, the mechanisms of change of the human psyche under the influence of education, the theory of formation of personal qualities of students through mental development. A pedagogue can effectively influence students in the educational process only by studying preschool pedagogy in connection with the system of psychological sciences.

In conclusion, it is permissible to say the following:

- by studying the science of preschool pedagogy, the theoretical foundations of education and upbringing of children of preschool age are mastered;
- Scientific and theoretical information is acquired in the work of educating competent individuals by studying the scientific research methods of preschool pedagogy.

In the words of Yusuf Khos Khajibev everyone should grow up worthy of the society.

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